

D5.3

First DEP Release

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Abstract

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Data Exploitation Platform, DEP, Big Data, AI, Credit Management, AAI

The first release of the Data Exploitation Platform (DEP) has been produced in RI-SCALE by the project's technical work packages and use cases. This release established the core foundations of the DEP. It includes the main technical components and applications of the DEP architecture, implemented either fully or partially, at least at a proof-of-concept level, across the areas of Data Life Cycle Management, AI Life Cycle Management, Access Control, Credit Management, and HPC integration. The requirements addressed and the functionalities delivered in this release are also presented. This document provides an overview of the release, including its features and a deployment guide to support validation by consortium data centres and research infrastructures.

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Terminology / Acronyms	
Term/Acronym	Definition
AAI	Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
CLI	Command Line Input
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DEP	Data Exploitation Platform
DPS	Data Preparation Service
GPU	Graphical Processing Unit
HPC	High Performance Computing
IAM	Identity Access Management
ML	Machine Learning
OAuth	Open Authorization
OIDC	OpenID Connect
RI	Research Infrastructure
SUC	Scientific Use Case
TUC	Technical Use Case
WP	Work Package
WSI	Whole Slide Image

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	6
1. Introduction	7
1.1 Scope of the Deliverable.....	7
1.2 Document Structure.....	7
2. DEP Architecture Overview	8
3. The First DEP Release	10
3.1. Consolidated Technical Achievements.....	10
3.2. Addressing Use Case Requirements.....	13
3.3. Use Case Components.....	14
3.3.1. Scientific Use Cases (SUC).....	15
3.3.2. Technical Use Cases (TUC).....	16
4. Conclusions and Next Steps	18
References	20
Annex: Dashboard Development	21

Table of Figures

- [Figure 1: High-level DEP Architecture](#)

Table of Tables

- [Table 1: The First DEP Release and its Technical Components](#)
- [Table 2: Data Management-related Requirements addressed by the 1st Release](#)
- [Table 3: AI-related Requirements addressed by the 1st Release](#)
- [Table 4: Access Management-related Requirements addressed by the 1st Release](#)

Executive Summary

RI-SCALE's ambition is to enable Research Infrastructures (RIs) unlock the full value of their data holdings by coupling with computing infrastructures and offering data for AI-powered applications. This vision is to be reached by "Data Exploitation Platforms", scalable environments that support 1) the secure transfer of data from RI data holdings to large computing resources (HPC, cloud), and 2) data analysis within those systems through AI platforms, then provide model training and inference capabilities.

This deliverable details the first release of the RI-SCALE Data Exploitation Platform (DEP). This first release implements the main technical pillars for the DEP and integrates these at a proof-of-concept level, reusing technologies that have been proven in previous projects:

- Data Life Cycle Management based on Rucio, FTS, Data Preparation Service (DPS),
- AI Life Cycle management based on Model Hub and AI Agent, Interlink, itwinai, xOpat Visualisation tool, yProv4ML,
- Access Control management based on ODRL Policy Repository, Open Policy Agent (OPA), Federated tokens,
- User Credit Management based on Resource Consumption Accounting for CPU, GPU, and Storage,
- Specialised hardware integration for GROQ cards.

The primary objective of this document is to give an overview of the release, including its features and deployment guides, facilitating the next phase of the project: final configuration of the release within the 2 participating compute centres, and validation of it by the 8 scientific and 4 technical use cases. The first DEP release is not yet an integrated and 'out-of-the-box' software solution, therefore strong cooperation between the DEP developers, the compute centres and the 12 use cases was put in place early on during the project.

The first DEP release implements all fundamental features of the DEP, representing 23% of all the functional and non-functional requirements that have been captured from these 8+4 use cases in the first 4 months of the project¹. The remaining 77% are scheduled for implementation in the second DEP release for March 2027. This deliverable details these requirements and indicates the progress towards the final DEP version.

¹ D5.1 Data Exploitation Platform Requirements and Design Considerations (<https://zenodo.org/records/15755803>)

1. Introduction

1.1 Scope of the Deliverable

This deliverable describes the components and functionalities included in the first release of the Data Exploitation Platform (DEP). It presents the initial service architecture and the core capabilities and modules that have been designed, implemented, and made available in this release. The document, therefore, reflects the current baseline of the DEP at this stage of the project.

The first DEP release constitutes a partial implementation of the overall platform vision and planned service portfolio. Accordingly, this deliverable establishes the reference point for the continued evolution of the DEP and for future deliverables that will document the extension of the platform towards its full intended functionality and operational maturity.

1.2 Document Structure

The structure of this deliverable contains the following sections. [Section 2](#) presents a high-level architecture of the DEP and its components. Components, capabilities and software repositories of the 1st release are described in [Section 3](#). Finally, [Section 4](#) expresses conclusions concerning the 1st release.

2. DEP Architecture Overview

The high-level DEP architecture has been produced in previous deliverables, and it is presented in [Figure 1](#) below. The main functions in the architecture are the following:

- **Data lifecycle management** to orchestrate intelligent, policy-based data transfers using tools such as Rucio and FTS. This enables transparent and efficient movement of large datasets to cloud or HPC environments for advanced analytics and AI applications.
- **AI lifecycle management** contains a set of complementary technology components designed to provide a coherent foundation for deploying, executing, and managing AI-driven scientific workflows within the DEP.
- **Credit management system** to track resource usage (e.g., CPU, GPU, storage, network) and related environmental impact (e.g., energy, Carbon Dioxide -CO₂- emission, water usage), translates these into credits via sustainability-focused policies (e.g., green-index discounts), and distributes credits to users through a centralised registry.
- **Access control** ensures secure and authenticated access for all interactions, controlling which users and systems can perform specific operations.

Figure 1: High-level DEP Architecture

This architecture is described in more detail in the following deliverables:

- D2.1 DEP Data Management Specification and Roadmap [R1]

- D3.1 AI Systems and Models Specification and Roadmap [[R2](#)]
- D4.1 Access Management Systems Specification and Roadmap [[R3](#)]
- D5.1 Data Exploitation Platform Requirements and Design Considerations [[R4](#)]
- D5.2 Validation Plan for Use Case Scenarios [[R5](#)]

3. The First DEP Release

The first DEP release contains the core platform components or their development versions. The content of the first version has been implemented in two directions, namely, on the one hand, to meet the requirements of the use cases, and on the other hand, to promote and enable the technical implementation as part of the DEP. It is also about the groundwork that needs to be done in order to get a solution that meets the requirements in the second release.

3.1. Consolidated Technical Achievements

This section presents the components of the first release and their technical implementation. The implementation of the DEP components is progressing in such a way that, in this release, the components of the key sub-areas of the architecture (presented above) have been implemented at least at the proof-of-concept level. From this stage, it is possible to iteratively progress toward the second release and ultimately to the final DEP.

In this first release, the level of integration of the technical components has not yet reached its final state.

[Table 1](#) presents the aforementioned architectural sub-areas to which the technical implementations belong, along with a description of their level of integration and the relevant links to the documentation.

Table 1: The First DEP Release and its Technical Components

Area	Component	Integration Status	Additional information
Data Life Cycle Management	Rucio and FTS	RI repository/data holding integration to the data orchestration service. Proof of Concept: S3 Integration	API guide: https://docs.google.com/document/d/1DEOvdgHZB0L6_y5heimpl3ciDolwVUeKjFkV/LpmUDLU/edit?usp=sharing
Data Life Cycle Management	Data Preparation Service (DPS)	Implementation of containerized DPS done with provenance logging. First version of the data replication and caching pipeline for ENES and BBMRI	https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/ri-scale-dashboard/blob/main/DPS_1st_DEP_RELEASE.md https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/ri-scale-dashboard/blob/main/DPS_1st_DEP_RELEASE.md https://github.com/RI-SCALE/climate-data-caching
AI Life Cycle management	Model Hub	The initial version is in use. Trainable models have been initiated. First version of	https://github.com/ri-scale/model-hub

		the trained models for use cases.	https://github.com/aicell-lab/bioengine-worker/tree/main/bioengine_apps/cellpose_finetuning https://github.com/RI-SCALE/hypermeteo-downscaling-plugin https://github.com/RI-SCALE/climate-data-usage-pipelines
AI Life Cycle Management	Interlink	Integrated with TUBITAK infrastructure	https://github.com/interlink-hq/interLink/releases/tag/O.6.1-pre4
AI Life Cycle Management	itwinai	Integrated with yProv4ML and Model Hub	https://github.com/interTwin-eu/itwinai/releases/tag/v0.4.2
AI Life Cycle Management	xOpat Visualisation tool	Deployed in MUSICA	https://github.com/SDNAFIO/RI-Scale-XOpat
AI Life Cycle Management	AI agent	Initial version of training model (Cellpose) done by using agent Biolmage Archive integration with Model Hub and BioEngine	MCP server for agent-controlled Cellpose training: https://hypha.aicell.io/bioimage-io/mcp/cellpose-finetuning/mcp Agents tab in the Model Hub with a Biolmage Finder for searching datasets in the Biolmage Archive: https://modelhub.riscale.eu/#/agents
AI Life Cycle Management	yProv4ML	Integrations of provenance information generated during machine learning processes implemented	HPCI-Lab/yProv4ML : A unified interface for logging and tracking provenance information in machine learning experiments, both on distributed as well as large scale experiments
Access Control	ODRL Policy Repository	Access control policies using the ODRL standard deployed	ODRL Policy Repository API specification has been published under https://github.com/RI-SCALE/odrl-policy-repository-api In parallel, a proof-of-concept implementation of the ODRL Policy Repository has been developed and

			<p>deployed (v1.0.0-rc2) in a test environment:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Source: https://github.com/rciam/rciam-odrl-policy-repo - Test deployment: https://odrl-repo.dep.dev.rciam.grnet.gr - Swagger UI available for interactive API testing at https://odrl-repo.dep.dev.rciam.grnet.gr/q/swagger-ui/
Access Control	Open Policy Agent (OPA)	Prototype of the runtime access control decisions using Open Policy Agent (OPA) implemented	A Policy Decision Point (PDP) prototype has been implemented using Open Policy Agent (OPA). A test deployment of OPA has been set up (https://opa-dev.cr.cnaf.infn.it:8085)
Access Control	AAI data encryption in transit	Implemented. Each AAI service should use HTTPS with TLS 1.3	
Access Control	Federated token management	Prepared and designed	
Access Control	UI for the exchanges with the users (proper consent)	Prepared	Based on internal survey results
Credit Management	Resource Consumption Accounting for CPU, GPU, and Storage	Designed (for 2nd release)	<p>Define Resource Consumption Metrics Description</p> <p>Investigate Metrics Collection Granularity and Availability Scope</p> <p>Define Accounting Topology for Resource Consumption Collection</p> <p>Initiate Metrics Collection from DEP Infrastructures</p>
HPC	GROQ	The GROQ AI accelerator hardware installed	In progress in TUC3

3.2. Addressing Use Case Requirements

D5.1, released in June 2025 and titled “Data Exploitation Platform Requirements and Design Considerations”², captured the list of requirements for the DEP from the 12 validation cases. D5.2, released in October 2025 and titled “Validation Plan for Use Case Scenarios”³, split the implementation of these requirements among the two envisaged DEP releases.

Based on D5.2, 23% of all the requirements were scheduled for the first DEP release. This 23% represent 20 requirements, out of the 88 total requirements. The second release of the DEP in M24 (March 2027) will fulfil the remaining 68 requirements.

The 1st release addresses all these scheduled requirements, and this is to be validated by the 8 scientific and 4 technical use cases. The validations will be performed between March-August 2026, and will be documented in D5.4 (to be released on 31/Aug/2026).

Tables 2, 3 and 4 detail the 20 requirements by areas that have been implemented by the first DEP release from D5.2.

Table 2: Data Management-related Requirements addressed by the 1st Release

Code	Title	Related task
RSREQ-21	Access to CMIPs climate datasets and reanalysis data (WP3 - T3.3)	Data Holdings Integration Framework (WP2-T2.4)
RSREQ-23	Results Delivery Mechanism from DEP to RIs	Data Orchestration Service (WP2-T2.1)
RSREQ-24	GitLab server for Code and Artifact Management	Computing Site Integration Interface (WP2-T2.5)
RSREQ-33	Data Preparation for Exploitation in the DEP	Data Preparation Module (WP2-T2.2)
RSREQ-90	Secure Access to Computing Sites	Computing Site Integration Interface (WP2-T2.5)
RSREQ-91	Integration of EISCAT data archives	Data Orchestration Service (WP2-T2.1)

Table 3: AI-related Requirements addressed by the 1st Release

Code	Title	Related task
RSREQ-10	Scalable AI solutions (WP3 - T3.1)	AI Computing Framework (WP3-T3.1)
RSREQ-13	AI Model Hub APIs & UI (WP3 - T3.2)	AI Model Hub (WP3-T3.2)
RSREQ-14	AI Model Hub AAI Integration (WP3 - T3.2)	AI Model Hub (WP3-T3.2)

² D5.1 Data Exploitation Platform Requirements and Design Considerations

(<https://zenodo.org/records/15755803>)

³ D5.2 Validation Plan for Use Case Scenarios (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17494163>)

RSREQ-17	Support development of ML models for anomaly detection (WP3-T3.3)	AI Computing Framework (WP3-T3.1)
RSREQ-20	Provide an AI model for statistical downscaling of climate projections (WP3-T3.3)	AI for Environmental Science (WP3-T3.3)
RSREQ-28	Support for WSI Inference in the AI Model Hub	AI Model Hub (WP3-T3.2)
RSREQ-40	Distributed ML framework is deployed on at least one of the EuroHPC systems DestinE uses	AI Computing Framework (WP3-T3.1)
RSREQ-95	Provide an ML model for anomaly detection in ESGF climate data usage (WP3-T3.3)	AI for Environmental Science (WP3-T3.3)
RSREQ-96	Support the development of AI models for the downscaling of climate projections	AI Computing Framework (WP3-T3.1)

Table 4: Access Management-related Requirements addressed by the 1st Release

Code	Title	Related task
RSREQ-36	Data Access and Embargo Rules	Policy-Based Authorization Framework (WP4-T4.1)
RSREQ-43	DestinE data should be secure in compliance with DestinE's security model and data access permissions	Policy-Based Authorization Framework (WP4-T4.1)
RSREQ-56	Encryption in transit	Privacy-First Compliance Layer (WP4-T4.3)
RSREQ-72	Authorisation Policy Language	Policy-Based Authorization Framework (WP4-T4.1)
RSREQ-82	UI for Authorisation Policy Authoring	Policy-Based Authorization Framework (WP4-T4.1)

3.3. Use Case Components

The first DEP release has not aimed to deliver all functionalities as an ‘out-of-the-box’ software solution, therefore strong cooperation between the DEP providers, the computational sites, and the 12 use cases was crucial for success. The first release of the DEP has been developed in co-design with the scientific use cases, and was supervised through bi-weekly use case meetings. This approach ensures that the development activities are driven by concrete, real-world requirements rather than solely by the objective of advancing technical capabilities.

While the use cases themselves are the subject of dedicated deliverables (D5.1 and D5.2), this section provides an overview of the specific DEP components each use case engages with in the context of the first release, and summarises the current implementation status of the use cases.

3.3.1. Scientific Use Cases (SUC)

SUC1 – Climate Scenarios and Risk Trend Analysis in Agriculture (ENES/HYP)

SUC1 primarily engages with the data management and AI computing components of the DEP. Climate datasets (CMIPs and reanalysis data, addressed by RSREQ-21) have been downloaded to the JSC cloud facility, and preprocessing is in progress. Integration with the itwinai distributed machine learning framework and the yProv [R6] ecosystem provenance tracking components (WP3) is underway to support traceability of the model training and the data engineering pipeline, with the goal of having a first trained model ready and documented for the first release.

SUC2 – Smart Detection of Anomalies in Climate Data Usage (ENES/CMCC)

SUC2 engages with the Data Orchestration Service (WP2-T2.1), data cleaning modules (WP2-T2.2) and the AI Computing Framework (WP3-T3.1). The use case focuses on detecting changes/anomalies in ESGF climate data usage (RSREQ-95) and requires adaptations to the data popularity service to retrieve data for the training and testing stages, which are ongoing. Integration of itwinai and yProv4ML components for tracking model developments into the machine learning model training code is actively in progress, with the first version targeting completion at the time of the first release.

SUC3 – Intelligent Scheduling of Radar Observations and Experiments (EISCAT)

SUC3 is closely linked to the integration of EISCAT data archives (RSREQ-91, addressed via WP2-T2.1). The use case team has been defining the prediction horizon relevant for scheduling experiments and identifying the spatial locations of most scientific value for the radar equipment. Discussions with the LTU and Neuraspace teams on space weather auxiliary data sources have been initiated. DEP integration discussions are ongoing, with file access mechanisms (Rucio/FTS) under consideration in WP2.

SUC4 – Space Debris and Anomaly Detection (EISCAT/Neuraspace)

SUC4 similarly relies on EISCAT data archive integration (RSREQ-36, RSREQ-91) and secure data access (RSREQ-90). Data access for LTU and Neuraspace has been arranged. The Neuraspace team has been performing exploratory data analysis and developing baseline models, with software prepared for cloud deployment. The use case also requires the Policy-Based Authorization Framework (WP4-T4.1) to enforce data access and embargo rules.

SUC5 – Colorectal Cancer Prediction with Explainable AI (MUG)

SUC5 engages prominently with the AI Model Hub (RSREQ-28, WP3-T3.2) for whole-slide image (WSI) inference and with HPC integration via the Computing Site Integration Interface (WP2-T2.5). Slide scanning and data transfer of WSIs from MMCI have been completed, with data stored on the Secure Cloud. A use-case-specific dashboard for data lifecycle management, model management, and HPC integration (MUSICA cluster) has been instantiated. Initial computational tests on the VSC5 cluster in Vienna have been conducted, with large-scale experiments planned once the DEP is fully

operational. The xOpat visualisation tool (WP3-T3.4) is being deployed to support pathology workflows.

SUC6 – Synthetic Data for Computational Pathology (MUG)

SUC6 is closely coupled with SUC5 in its infrastructure requirements and equally relies on the MUSICA cluster, the AI Model Hub, and the Data Preparation Service (WP2-T2.2). A publication on synthetic data generation is in progress. Access to the MUSICA cluster is being prepared alongside SUC5, and compression capabilities (TUC2) will be integrated once the DPS is online.

SUC7 – Foundational Models for Heterogeneous Biological Image Data (EMBL/KTH)

SUC7 engages with the BioImage Archive (BIA) data holdings via WP2 integration work and with the AI Model Hub and BioEngine (WP3-T3.4). EMBL-EBI has developed scripts to query the BIA API and responded to the storage systems questionnaire. The BIA API has been extended to support image-level search, which is a prerequisite for the use case. A BIA dataset for Cellpose model training has been shared with KTH, and this training pipeline is close to completion. Integration between BIA and the Model Hub via BioEngine is increasing. An example is presented in the [Annex](#).

SUC8 – Generative AI-Powered Assistant for Data Discovery and Analysis (EMBL/KTH)

SUC8 is centred on the AI Model Hub (WP3-T3.2) and the data access layer (WP2). KTH is building an AI agent-based chatbot for navigating image data in the BioImage Archive, with scripts for model loading from the AI Model Hub and dataset storage in Hypha already developed. Image search API and agent integration have been done and shared with KTH. The first version of the BioImage Finder for searching datasets is in the BioImage Archive [[RZ](#)]. The core components — dataset search, model search, and model execution through the agent — are functionally in place. An example is presented in the [Annex](#).

3.3.2. Technical Use Cases (TUC)

TUC1 – Scalability on EuroHPC with Destination Earth (ECMWF)

TUC1 is focused on the AI Computing Framework (RSREQ-40, WP3-T3.1) and its deployment on EuroHPC systems. Discussions to utilise EuroHPC facilities such as LUMI, Leonardo or Mare Nostrum have been initiated, and DestinE data access (RSREQ-43) is being addressed in coordination with ECMWF. This use case will primarily mature in the second DEP release.

TUC2 – Advanced Image Compression (Comprimato/MUG)

TUC2 is technically integrated with the Data Preparation Service (WP2-T2.2), where compression is planned as a modular component of the DPS pipeline. Collaboration with Comprimato is active, and benchmarking of compression algorithms will commence once the MUSICA cluster is operational and the DPS is available for testing.

TUC3 – Green Computing Improvement (fragmentix/TU Wien)

TUC3 is linked to the AI Computing Framework (WP3-T3.1) and focuses on evaluating the energy efficiency of inference workloads using GROQ cards. TU Wien has received and installed the GROQ hardware, and network connectivity issues are in the process of being resolved. Software evaluation for benchmarking is underway.

TUC4 – Credit Management System (GRNET)

TUC4 addresses the credit management and resource consumption accounting components of the DEP (WP4-T4.4, RSREQ-27). The Credit Management System is being developed by GRNET and will support resource accounting for CPU, GPU, and storage usage across the platform. AAI integration (RSREQ-14) is a prerequisite, and progress is being tracked through the Technical Coordination Board (TCB). This use case will reach operational maturity primarily in the second DEP release.

4. Conclusions and Next Steps

The first release of the DEP has focused on establishing the core functionalities and key service domains, based on the requirements and specifications defined in the project documentation. This initial implementation provides the essential building blocks of the DEP, such as workflows where data holdings are integrated with computing resources and AI life cycle management, and AI models have integrated with the platform. This has also required access control mechanisms implemented with the platform.

As noted in this deliverable, the clear majority of the planned DEP functionalities will be incorporated in the second platform release. This subsequent release will enable a more comprehensive view of the overall DEP service offering and its integrated capability set. The development approach will continue to follow an iterative methodology, ensuring that user requirements and feedback are taken into account throughout the design and implementation phases.

The central objective of the second DEP release will be the integration of the functionalities established in the first release, together with the implementation of additional planned capabilities. Particular emphasis will be placed on the development and deployment of functionalities supporting the management and exploitation of sensitive data. The second release will also focus on the unified user experience and its development, together with use cases.

Next steps are :

- Complete the deployment of the 4 DEPs at TUW and TUBITAK (2-2 each), including their connection to 4 RI data holdings. This will complete the milestone M2.1 by project month 13 (31/Mar/26).
- Complete the configuration of the AI frameworks within the 4 DEP installations. This will complete the milestone M3.1 by project month 14 (30/Apr/2026).
- Fine-tune the access management frameworks within the 4 DEPs, enabling coherent access to resources for the validators. This will complete the milestone M4.1 by project month 15 (31/May/2026).
- Validate the 4 DEPs via the 8 scientific use cases (2-2 from each of the 4 RIs), and by the 4 technical use cases. The work will be documented in D5.4 by project month 18 (31/Aug/2026). The validation will assess:
 - Validation the setups of requirements by running the scientific validation use cases, and assess that the 23% of the total requirements are met.
 - Validation also gives the opportunity to update the list of requirements and refine the activities of the second release.

The whole process will be facilitated in the technical workshop in March (online) and in the workshop in June.

References

Reference	
No	Description/Link
R1	D2.1 DEP Data Management Specification and Roadmap, https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16993600
R2	D3.1 AI Systems and Models Specification and Roadmap, https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16994162
R3	D4.1 Access Management Systems Specification and Roadmap, https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16994162
R4	D5.1 Data Exploitation Platform Requirements and Design Considerations, https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16993600
R5	D5.2 Validation Plan for Use Case Scenarios, https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17494163
R6	yProv ecosystem: https://hpci-lab.github.io/yprov.github.io/
R7	Agents in the Model Hub: https://modelhub.riscale.eu/#/agents

Annex: Dashboard Development

Current development for Bioluming use cases (SUC7 and SUC8):

Example 1: Data Transfers in SUC7

The screenshot displays the 'Data Transfers' dashboard for the project 'UC7 - CRC Prediction'. The interface includes a sidebar with navigation options like Dashboard, Model Hub, Datasets, Data Transfers, HPC Jobs, Compute Quotas, Directory, Negotiator, About, and Settings. The main content area shows a summary of transfer counts and a table of active transfers.

ID	Project	Route	Size	Progress	Status	Actions
txf-a1b2...	UC7 - CRC Prediction	BBMRI-AT Storage → MUSICA	11.4 TB	100%	Completed	View
txf-b2c3...	UC7 - CRC Prediction	BBMRI-AT Storage → MUG-SX	8.1 TB	67%	In Progress	View, Stop, Delete
txf-e5f6...	UC7 - CRC Prediction	BBMRI-AT Storage → MUSICA	1.6 TB	100%	Failed	View, Refresh

Example 2: Dataset in SUC7

The screenshot displays the 'Datasets' page in the RI-SCALE application. The interface includes a sidebar with navigation options like Dashboard, Model Hub, and Datasets. The main content area features a header with the project name 'UC7 - CRC Prediction' and a sub-header 'Datasets'. Below this, there are four summary cards: '3 Total Datasets', '33,5K Total WSIs', '41,5 TB Total Size', and '2 Active'. A search bar and filter dropdowns for 'Data Type' and 'Status' are present. The dataset list contains three items: 'Lymph Node WSI Collection A' (active), 'Lymph Node WSI Collection B' (active), and 'Synthetic WSI Output v1' (processing). Each card provides details such as source, description, WSI count, size, and storage location.

Dataset Name	Status	Source	Description	WSIs	Size	Storage	Assigned To
Lymph Node WSI Collection A	active	BBMRI-AT / Medical University of Graz	Primary lymph node whole-slide images for colorectal cancer analysis.	15.0K	18.5 TB	MUG	UC7-CRC, UC7-XAI
Lymph Node WSI Collection B	active	MMCI (Masaryk Memorial Cancer Institute)	Secondary lymph node collection for model validation and testing.	8.5K	10.2 TB	BBMRI-ERIC WSI Repository	UC7-CRC
Synthetic WSI Output v1	processing	Generated by PathGAN-XL	First generation of synthetic whole-slide images for validation.	10.0K	12.8 TB	MUG	UC8-Synth, UC7-CRC

Example 3: Model Hub

